

Gallium triiodide as a highly efficient and mild catalyst for the diethyl acetalization of carbonyl compounds

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Abstract : Diethyl acetals were obtained from carbonyl compounds in good to excellent yields under mild reaction conditions in the presence of triethyl orthoformate and a catalytic amount of gallium triiodide in anhydrous ethanol.

Keywords : Diethyl acetals, carbonyl compound, gallium triiodide.

Introduction

Conversion of carbonyl compounds to acetals is an important and widely used strategy for the protection of carbonyl groups in the process of organic synthesis¹. Besides, acetals themselves are useful intermediates in various organic transformations². Thus, a variety of methods have been developed for the preparation of acetals³. One of the most attractive approach for acetalization is by treatment of the carbonyl compounds with trialkyl orthoformate in the presence of acid catalysts, such as HCl⁴, FeCl₃⁵, Amberlyst-15⁶, DDQ⁷, ZrCl₄⁸, Bi(OTf)₃⁹, B₁₀H₁₄¹⁰, LiBF₄¹¹. However, many of these procedures have some limitations in terms of the requirement of a large excess of reagents, long reaction time, strong reaction conditions (high temperature), moisture-sensitive and expensive reagents, etc. Therefore, there is still considerable interest in finding more convenient and effective methods for the conversion of carbonyl groups to acetals.

The catalyst gallium triiodide can be easily prepared *in situ* by the reaction of gallium with iodine¹², which can bring some advantages for its application. It has been employed as an effective Lewis acid catalyst for Sakurai reaction, tetrahydropyranylation of alcohols and phenols, the coupling reaction of carbonyl compounds, amines and diethyl phosphate, and the synthesis of 3-substituted indoles¹³. Compared to other Lewis acids, the synthetic application of GaI₃ has not been fully explored. Herein, we wish to disclose a new application of gallium triiodide

as a highly efficient catalyst for the diethyl acetalization of carbonyl compounds (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

The GaI₃ used in the reaction was easily generated *in situ* by the reaction of gallium metal and iodine in ethanol. As shown in the Table 1, the acetalization proceeded smoothly to give diethyl acetals in good to excellent yields catalyzed by as little as 1 mol% GaI₃. The catalyst loading could even reduce to 0.1 mol% to give a satisfactory result in the expense of longer reaction time (entry 1). It seemed that solvent played a very important role in the reaction. Taking the case of benzaldehyde acetalization as example, when the reaction was carried out in THF, only low yield of the corresponding diethyl acetal was formed after 3 h (<10%, entry 1). In the reaction catalyzed by DDQ⁷, 2a was obtained in 95% after stirring for 10 h, whereas the present procedure results 2a in 98% within 25 min. It may be noted that acid-sensitive substrate such as piperonal (entry 5) was diethylacetalized without the formation of any by-product which was nor-

Table 1. Diethyl acetalization of carbonyl compounds catalyzed by GaI₃^a

Entry	R ₁	R ₂	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b
1	Ph	H	25 (60 ^c , 180 ^d)	98 (98 ^c , <10 ^d) (2a)
2	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	H	5	94 (2b)
3	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	H	4	93 (2c)
4	3-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	H	5	95 (2d)
5	3,4-OCH ₂ OC ₆ H ₃	H	30	95 (2e)
6	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	H	60 (15 ^e)	98 (99 ^e) (2f)
7	3-BrC ₆ H ₄	H	15	99 (2g)
8	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	H	120	80 (2h)
9	PhCH ₂ CH ₂	H	80	96 (2i)
10	CH ₃ CH(Ph)CH ₂	H	70	94 (2j)
11	PhCH=CH	H	5	96 (2k)
12	Ph	CH ₃	180	55 (2l)
13 ^f	Ph	Ph	420	30 (2m)
14 ^f			480	32 (2n)

^aAll reactions were carried out in anhydrous ethanol using 1.0 mol% of GaI₃ at room temperature unless other description. ^bIsolated yields of products. ^cThe reaction was carried out by using 0.1 mol% of GaI₃. ^dThe reaction was carried out in THF for 3 h. ^e10 mol% catalyst was used. ^f4 mol% catalyst was used.

mally encountered under acidic conditions. Moreover, α,β -unsaturated aldehyde was easily acetalized without concomitant of double-bond isomerization (entry 11). This indicates that the reaction conditions are relatively mild and not sufficiently acidic to cause isomerization of the double bond. In the case of aliphatic aldehydes, the acetalization also afforded the desired products in excellent yields (entries 9, 10). However, compared with aldehydes, acetophenone required longer reaction time and gave a moderate yield of 55% (entry 12), which could be due to steric factors. Diaryl ketones are quite resistant to the standard conditions for acetalization¹⁰. Under the present catalyst, benzophenone and 9-fluorenone could be converted to its diethyl acetal in 30% and 32% yields respectively using 4 mol% of GaI₃ (entries 13, 14).

In conclusion, we have disclosed that GaI₃ could serve as a highly efficient and mild Lewis acid catalyst for the diethyl acetalization of carbonyl compounds. The mild reaction conditions, short reaction time, simple operational procedure and high yields of products make the present procedure attractive.

Experimental

All reagents were purchased from commercial sources. Ethanol was dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and

aldehydes were freshly distilled prior to use. All products are known compounds; they were characterized by ¹H NMR and IR. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC-300 spectrometer for solutions in CDCl₃ with tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard. IR spectra were recorded on a Bruker-EQUINOX55 spectrometer.

A representative procedure for the acetalization of benzaldehyde with gallium triiodide :

Gallium metal (0.04 mmol) and iodine (0.06 mmol) were added in anhydrous ethanol. The mixture was stirred under nitrogen atmosphere until the color of iodine disappeared and the mixture became a transparent liquid. To the readily prepared solution of GaI₃ were added benzaldehyde (4 nmol) and triethyl orthoformate (4.8 mmol). The resulting mixture was stirred at room temperature for 25 min and then quenched with NaHCO₃. The solid inorganic material was filtered off and solvent was evaporated to afford the crude product which was purified by column chromatography on alumina gel with petroleum ether and ethyl acetate (15 : 1) to give the pure 2a in 98% yield.

2a⁷ : ν_{\max} : 2976, 2929, 2881, 1490, 1450, 1338, 1306, 1207, 1113, 1054, 749, 702 cm⁻¹; δ 7.50–7.33 (5H, m), 5.51 (1H, s), 3.66–3.51 (4H, m), 1.27–1.22 (6H, m); 2b⁷ : ν_{\max} : 2976, 2927, 2879, 1512, 1445, 1338, 1203, 1175, 1112, 1055, 917, 842, 807, 777 cm⁻¹; δ 7.41–7.38 (2H, m), 7.21–7.18 (2H, m), 5.51 (1H, s), 3.67–3.53 (4H, m), 2.37 (3H, s), 1.29–1.24 (6H, m); 2c⁷ : ν_{\max} : 2976, 2932, 2882, 1605, 1461, 1302, 1249, 1169, 1094, 1053, 911, 832, 733 cm⁻¹; δ 7.41–7.37 (2H, m), 6.91–6.86 (2H, m), 5.46 (1H, s), 3.81 (3H, s), 3.63–3.48 (4H, m), 1.28–1.21 (6H, m); 2d^{3b} : ν_{\max} : 2976, 2931, 2882, 1601, 1487, 1457, 1335, 1261, 1165, 1110, 1054, 888, 771 cm⁻¹; δ 7.30–6.84 (4H, m), 5.47 (1H, s), 3.82 (3H, s), 3.65–3.51 (4H, m), 1.26–1.21 (6H, m); 2e⁹ : ν_{\max} : 2976, 2927, 2883, 1490, 1441, 1328, 1247, 1102, 1049, 935, 793 cm⁻¹; δ 6.98–6.77 (3H, m), 5.95 (2H, s), 5.40 (1H, s), 3.64–3.48 (4H, s), 1.28–1.21 (6H, m); 2f⁷ : ν_{\max} : 2976, 2926, 2881, 1598, 1488, 1445, 1396, 1336, 1296, 1205, 1112, 1089, 1055, 918, 803 cm⁻¹; δ 7.43–7.39 (2H, m), 7.34–7.31 (2H, m), 5.48 (1H, s), 3.62–3.49 (4H, m), 1.25–1.21 (6H, m); 2g¹⁴ : ν_{\max} : 2976, 2928, 2881, 1571, 1472, 1333, 1197, 1113, 1054, 782 cm⁻¹; δ 7.64–7.19 (4H, m), 5.46 (1H, s), 3.65–3.50 (4H, m), 1.26–1.21 (6H, m); 2h^{3a} : ν_{\max} : 2978, 2920, 2885, 1532, 1362, 1270, 1111, 1059, 785, 741 cm⁻¹; δ 7.84–7.79 (2H, m), 7.62–7.57 (1H, m), 7.49–7.43 (1H, m), 6.03 (1H, s), 3.76–3.55 (4H, m), 1.26–1.22 (6H, m); 2i¹¹ : ν_{\max} : 2975, 2929, 2876, 1495.

1451, 1375, 1344, 1129, 1062, 747, 699 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.32–7.19 (5H, m), 4.51 (1H, t, J 5.7 Hz), 3.70–3.49 (4H, m), 2.71 (2H, t, J 7.8 Hz), 1.99–1.93 (2H, m), 1.26–1.21 (6H, m); $^2\text{j}^{15}$: ν_{max} : 2975, 2916, 2850, 1492, 1451, 1222, 1032, 780 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.19–7.36 (5H, m), 4.48 (1H, d, J 6.49 Hz), 3.70–3.75 (1H, m), 3.45–3.61 (2H, m), 3.31–3.36 (1H, m), 3.00–3.55 (1H, m), 1.32 (3H, d, J 7.07 Hz), 1.22 (3H, t, J 7.02 Hz), 1.07 (3H, t, J 7.02 Hz); $^2\text{k}^7$: ν_{max} : 2977, 2929, 2878, 1626, 1449, 1373, 1336, 1124, 1053, 970, 731 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.43–7.23 (5H, m), 6.71 (1H, d, J 16.1 Hz), 6.22 (1H, dd, J_1 5.2 Hz, J_2 16.1 Hz), 5.07 (1H, d, J 5.2 Hz), 3.77–3.52 (4H, m), 1.28–1.21 (6H, m); $^2\text{l}^7$: ν_{max} : 2956, 2923, 2852, 1463, 1378, 1264, 1218, 1167, 1054, 1017 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.55–7.26 (5H, m), 3.52–3.34 (4H, m), 1.56 (3H, s), 1.25–1.17 (6H, m); $^2\text{m}^7$: ν_{max} : 2974, 2926, 2881, 1445, 1385, 1241, 1206, 1111, 1055, 1014, 919, 785, 699 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.57–7.19 (10H, m), 3.38–3.30 (4H, m), 1.28–1.21 (6H, m); $^2\text{n}^{16}$: ν_{max} : 2978, 2928, 1403, 1240, 1079, 908 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.25–7.40 (4H, m), 7.54–7.61 (4H, m), 3.45 (4H, q, J 7.02 Hz), 1.16 (6H, t, J 7.02 Hz).

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